

Lung cancer: Etiology, prevalence, diagnosis and treatment

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ABSTRACT

Lung cancer, identified by the unchecked proliferation of aberrant cells within the lungs, stands as a principal cause of death from cancer on a worldwide scale. The origins of lung cancer are complex, stemming from a web of genetic predispositions, environmental exposures, and lifestyle choices. Tobacco use is the primary culprit, implicated in approximately 85% of lung cancer instances, while other factors include contact with harmful substances like radon and asbestos, air contamination, genetic inheritance, pre-existing lung conditions, and detrimental health habits. The World Health Organization reports that lung cancer tops the list of most prevalent cancers globally, with over two million new cases and close to 1.8 million fatalities in 2020. The process for identifying this disease involves several stages, starting with a thorough review of the patient's health history and a physical exam, proceeding to diagnostic imaging, examination of sputum under a microscope, tissue biopsy, molecular analysis, and then determining the stage of the cancer. Employing early detection measures, such as low-dose CT scans, is vital for enhancing patient survival rates. Approaches to treating lung cancer are highly individualized, taking into account the cancer's classification and progression, the patient's overall health, and their treatment preferences. Options may include surgical removal of a portion or entire lung section in early-stage non-small cell lung cancer, along with methods to directly target the cancer, bolster the immune response, or manage symptoms. The intricate nature of lung cancer calls for a coordinated treatment strategy devised by a team of specialists, including oncologists, radiologists, pathologists, surgeons, and respiratory experts, to secure the most favorable treatment outcomes. Such a team crafts a detailed and customized plan for each patient. Despite progress in detection and treatment technologies, the high incidence rate of lung cancer highlights an ongoing need for research and better preventative measures.

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INTRODUCTION

Lung cancer, a leading cause of cancer-related mortality globally, stands as a formidable challenge in the realm of public health. Characterized by the uncontrolled growth of abnormal cells in one or both lungs, this malignancy often goes undetected until its advanced stages, making it particularly lethal. The primary types, non-small cell lung cancer and small cell lung cancer, each present with different growth rates and patterns, necessitating distinct treatment approaches. Major risk factors include smoking, exposure to secondhand smoke, and environmental toxins. Recent advances in diagnostics, therapeutics, and preventative measures have offered some hope in the battle against this disease, yet the statistics remain alarming. This article aims to provide a comprehensive overview of lung cancer, from its etiology and symptoms to current treatment options and ongoing research, shedding light on its implications for patients, caregivers, healthcare systems, and society at large (1-3).

Etiology

Lung cancer's etiology, or cause, is multifactorial, involving a complex interplay of genetic, environmental, and lifestyle factors. Understanding these factors is critical to developing effective prevention strategies and risk-reduction measures (4).

Smoking: Undoubtedly, smoking is the most significant risk factor for lung cancer, responsible for approximately 85% of all lung cancer cases. This includes not only active smoking but also exposure to secondhand smoke. Cigarette smoke contains over 7,000 chemicals, many of which are proven carcinogens that can damage the cells lining the lungs, leading over time to genetic mutations and the development of cancer (5).

Environmental Exposures: Environmental factors also play a significant role in the development of lung cancer. Exposure to radon, a naturally occurring radioactive gas that can accumulate in homes and other buildings, is the second leading cause of lung cancer in many countries. Other environmental carcinogens include asbestos, certain forms of silica, and diesel exhaust, which are often encountered in specific occupational settings (4).

Air Pollution: Chronic exposure to air pollution, particularly fine particulate matter and pollutants resulting from the burning of fossil fuels, has been shown to increase the risk of lung cancer (4).

Genetic Factors: A small but notable percentage of lung cancer cases can be attributed to inherited genetic factors. Certain genetic mutations increase susceptibility to the disease, and these can be passed down through generations. People with a family history of lung cancer, especially among immediate relatives, have a higher risk, suggesting a genetic predisposition (4).

Previous Lung Disease: Individuals with a history of certain lung diseases, including chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and tuberculosis, have a higher risk of developing lung cancer (3).

Lifestyle Factors: Certain lifestyle factors, such as a diet low in fruits and vegetables, lack of physical activity, and alcohol consumption, can contribute to lung cancer risk. These factors may interact with other risk factors, like smoking, to further increase the risk (5).

Prevalence

Lung cancer stands as a critical public health challenge, with its high rates of occurrence and mortality underscoring its substantial impact on global health. Its spread is shaped by a range of elements, including the rate of smoking, environmental factors, and the demographic characteristics of the population.

The WHO indicates that lung cancer holds the position as the leading type of cancer globally, with it being the cause of approximately 2.1 million newly diagnosed cases and 1.8 million

deaths in 2020. This accounts for about 11.6% of all new cancer diagnoses and is the cause of almost 20% of all cancer-related deaths. The regions with the highest recorded rates of lung cancer—North America, Europe, and East Asia—mirror the intense levels of smoking and exposure to industrial pollutants in these areas (5,6).

Diagnosis

Diagnosing lung cancer involves a multi-step process designed to identify the presence of the disease, determine its type and stage, and inform the most appropriate treatment plan. Here are the key components of lung cancer diagnosis (7):

Medical History and Physical Examination: A thorough understanding of a patient's medical history, including symptoms, smoking history, occupational exposures, and family history of cancer, is the first step. This is followed by a physical examination where the doctor checks for physical signs of lung cancer (7).

Imaging Studies: Imaging tests provide pictures of the inside of the body and are critical in diagnosing lung cancer. A chest X-ray is often the first test, but it can only show abnormal growth, not determine if it's cancerous. More detailed imaging is obtained via computed tomography (CT) scans, positron emission tomography (PET) scans, or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) to reveal small lesions and determine if the cancer has spread to other parts of the body (8).

Sputum Cytology: In this test, a sample of sputum (mucus) is analyzed under a microscope to detect cancer cells. It's most useful in patients with centrally located tumors that produce sputum (9).

Biopsy: This is the definitive method for diagnosing lung cancer. A biopsy involves removing a small amount of tissue from the suspected area for examination under a microscope. Several techniques can be used, including bronchoscopy, CT-guided needle biopsy, endobronchial ultrasound-guided biopsy, or even surgical biopsy (9).

Molecular Testing: If lung cancer is confirmed, further testing is often done on the biopsy sample to identify specific genes, proteins, and other factors unique to the tumor. This molecular profiling can help determine whether targeted therapies might be effective treatment options (8).

Staging: Once lung cancer is diagnosed, the extent (stage) of the cancer is determined to guide treatment decisions. This involves further tests to see if the cancer has spread within the lungs or to other parts of the body. Staging varies depending on the type of lung cancer, but generally includes Stage I (early stage, localized cancer) through Stage IV (advanced cancer that has spread to other areas) (7).

Early detection of lung cancer greatly enhances the likelihood of successful treatment. Therefore, screening is recommended for high-risk individuals, such as heavy smokers and those with a significant family history of lung cancer. The primary method of screening is low-dose computed tomography (LDCT), which has been shown to reduce lung cancer mortality by detecting cancers at earlier, more treatable stages (7).

Treatment

Treatment approaches for lung cancer are tailored to suit individual circumstances, taking into account the specific type and progression of the cancer, the general health of the patient, as well as the patient's own treatment preferences. The main strategies for managing lung cancer consist of surgical intervention, radiation therapy, chemotherapy, targeted therapy, immunotherapy, and care aimed at providing relief from symptoms (9).

Surgery: Typically the initial mode of treatment for early-stage non-small cell lung cancers (NSCLC) that remain confined and haven't metastasized. The surgical method chosen is

contingent on the tumor's size and position, and can range from: Lobectomy: The most prevalent surgical procedure for lung cancer, involving the excision of the lung lobe harboring the tumor. Segmentectomy or wedge resection: Involves the removal of a segment or a small wedge of the lobe where the tumor is situated. Pneumonectomy: Entails the complete removal of one lung and is generally reserved for cases where the tumor is centrally located within the lung (10).

Radiation Therapy: This treatment uses high-energy rays or particles to kill cancer cells. It can be used as the main treatment for patients who can't undergo surgery, before surgery to shrink tumors, after surgery to kill any remaining cells, or for palliation in advanced stages of the disease (11).

Chemotherapy: This involves the use of drugs to kill cancer cells or stop them from dividing. Chemotherapy can be administered systemically (through the bloodstream) or directly into the lungs. It may be used before surgery to shrink tumors, after surgery to kill any remaining cells, or as the main treatment for advanced lung cancer (11).

Targeted Therapy: This newer form of treatment targets specific genes or proteins in cancer cells that help them grow and divide. It's mainly used for advanced lung cancers that have certain gene mutations such as EGFR, ALK, and ROS1 (12).

Immunotherapy: This is a type of treatment that stimulates the body's immune system to fight cancer. It's primarily used for advanced lung cancers and can be very effective for cancers with high levels of PD-L1 expression or for those with specific genetic changes (13-15).

Palliative Care: This is a specialized form of care aimed at providing relief from pain and other symptoms of cancer. It's essential at all stages of the disease and can be given alongside curative treatments (15).

It's crucial to note that due to the complexities and variations in lung cancer, a multidisciplinary approach involving a team of specialists including oncologists, radiologists, pathologists, surgeons, and pulmonologists often provides the best patient outcomes. This team works together to create a comprehensive treatment plan tailored to each patient's unique situation (16).

CONCLUSIONS

Lung cancer, driven by an array of genetic, environmental, and lifestyle factors, continues to be a significant global health concern. The prospects for early detection, treatment, and improved survival rates rest upon ongoing advancements in diagnostics, therapies, and preventative measures, underpinned by a holistic, patient-centric care approach.

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